

RELIABLE MULTIHOP VORONOI LEACH FOR EFFICIENT WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Energy efficient processes are substantially important in Wireless Sensor Networks, especially in communication processes. In order to lower energy utilization on *LEACH*, Voronoi diagram-based clusters were presented that can bring a distance relationship among the given set of nodes. Multihop Voronoi *LEACH* was proposed to further reduce the communication energy expenditure between sensor nodes and cluster heads within Voronoi region. However, the method may often experience communication interruptions if the data to be transferred from sensor node to cluster head in high volumes or frequent data transfers. In this article, we propose an energy efficient wireless sensor network protocol called Reliable Multihop Voronoi *LEACH*, which is suitable for bulk data transfer in sensor network applications. Simulation results determine the performance of proposed method.

Keywords: *Sensors, Wireless Sensor Networks, Energy Saving, LEACH, Voronoi Diagrams.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, Wireless Sensor Network (*WSN*)s have been used in many surveillance applications. These applications include in the area of mining industry, defense systems, military applications, chemical plants, security surveillance, and nuclear plants. Due to the nature of the environment for these applications, the sensors are randomly scattered on the surveillance area and observe the geographic area. Due to the conditions of the environment in deployment area, the *WSN* poses many challenges, especially limited battery power. Once the battery power is depleted, the sensor mote is considered dead, and communication network structure is changed. Hence, the energy efficient communication infrastructure is needed for *WSN*. In the literature, many energy efficient methods are proposed for *WSN* [5][6][12][13]. The first cluster-based methodology for *WSN* is the Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchical (*LEACH*)[4]. In this method, the Sensor Nodes (*SN*) forms clusters and it includes a Cluster Head (*CH*), see Figure 1.

The election of cluster head in *LEACH* is based on the following formula

$$T(n) = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \frac{P}{1 - P * (r \bmod \frac{1}{P})} & \text{if } n \in G \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

P =The value of probability to become *CH*

G = List of nodes, which were not *CH*

r = the present node

Figure 1: The Cluster Based *WSN* Model

In order to optimize the energy expenditure for the data transfers in *WSN*, the researchers used a computational geometry structure the Voronoi diagram for forming sensor network clusters, see Figure 2. All the sensors within Voronoi region

need to transfer the environmental data to the Voronoi Vertex, i.e. cluster head. The basic objective of the method is to optimize the distances between the sensor nodes and their cluster head [19]. The method optimizes energy consumption and increase the lifespan of the network WSN.

Figure 2: Voronoi Diagram with eleven vertices

Energy consumption is directly proportional to the distance travelled by the data through the network. The distance here is the Euclidean distance among the sensors. The *Multihop Voronoi LEACH* (MV-LEACH) [23] considers the distance between a pair of sensors and improves energy efficiency of *VOR-LEACH*[19]. The basic idea of the *MV-LEACH* is that the multihop communications between a sensor and cluster head consume less communication energy compared to a single-hop long distance transmission, which has high energy consumption. However, the method does not consider the real conditions of the sensor nodes in the multihop transmissions. In general, the surveillance systems continuously send data from sensing area to the cluster head. In other words, bulk data transfers may lead to energy depletion from any of the sensor nodes in *MV-LEACH* path. This type of problem may cause problems such as network topology changes, and unreachability of sensor's data to the *CH* from the sensor's surveillance area. There is few clustering algorithms proposed in the literature for *WSN* [21][24][25]. All these methods focus on identifying the set of cluster heads to establish the stability of network. However, these methods face same problem of communication disruptions from

SN to *CH*. By focusing on these problems, we propose a new method called *Reliable Multihop Voronoi LEACH (RMV-LEACH)*, which is robust for high volumes of data transfers in *WSN*, and it is common in *WSN* applications.

The remaining portion of the paper is arranged as follows; Section II reveals literature review on the paper. Section III proposes a new methodology *RMV-LEACH*. Section IV presents simulation outcomes, whereas Section V concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

The straightforward objective of the research work is to minimize the energy consumption of the wireless sensor network. In the literature, various protocols exist for energy efficient communications [10][11][12][13][18][22]. Among them, the protocol *LEACH* is the first cluster constructed communication protocol for energy efficiency in *WSN* [4]. A *WSN* collects environmental data through sensor devices and transmits the data to a specified place by the communication system [14]. In general, sensor devices have limitations on energy resources [15]. Hence, it is important to explore and do the research on energy efficient communication systems for *WSN*. The operational process of *LEACH* method is broadly split into two phases [4]. In Phase I, the clusters are selected. Phase II of *LEACH* protocol is committed to transfer data from sensor node to its cluster head, which aggregates data of the cluster and retransmits it to the base-station.

In the literature, a few improvements of the *LEACH* protocol are made to enhance the lifespan of *WSN* and provide stable communication at the same time. The researchers in [1] proposed a sequential *LEACH (S-LEACH)* protocol. This method maintains the sufficient number of cluster heads at every iteration till the first node spends all its energy. Another method, the *E-LEACH* protocol chooses the cluster head based on the outstanding energy levels of sensor devices in the network [16]. In the *E-LEACH* method, the sensor having maximum outstanding energy is chosen as the *CH*, which improves network lifespan. In the *K-LEACH* protocol, the K-medoids algorithm is used to choose the *CHs*. This protocol enhances the network lifetime by balancing the load of the sensor network [15].

An author proposed a *D-LEACH* protocol, in which the probability functions are used in deciding for the transmission of data coming from the sensor nodes [2]. In Hierarchical *LEACH* protocol, three types of nodes exist in the network [17]. The level 1 nodes collect surveillance data from the environment and the level 2 nodes exist beyond the communication range of the base-station, whereas the level 3 nodes are found inside a predefined range of the base-station [17]. An author proposed *CS-LEACH* protocol, which uses Intelligent sleeping mechanism (*ISM*) procedure to turn a certain percentage of sensor nodes to go to the sleep mode for saving battery power of the sensor nodes [3]. Another method on reducing energy expenditure in wireless sensor networks is based on reducing data redundancy during the intra-cluster data transmission [22]. This method computes the intersection areas of the sensor nodes and avoids sending the same data by the more than one sensor node to the cluster head.

A Voronoi diagram is a computational geometry structure, which specifies the distance relation among given points [7]. The formal procedure for creating Voronoi diagram is specified in [7]. However, this is a centralized algorithm, and it is very difficult to use in wireless sensor network due to the limitations of the network. The localized procedure for constructing Voronoi diagram for wireless networks is specified in [5][6].

A method called Voronoi Leach (*Vor-LEACH*) was proposed to optimize the communication energy efficiency based on the distance parameter between a sensor and its cluster head [19]. In this method, first it computes cluster heads based on the criteria given in the *LEACH* protocol [4]. After the cluster heads are elected, it constructs the Voronoi diagram with the elected set of cluster heads using the algorithm provided in the paper [5][6]. Once the Voronoi regions are constructed, all the sensors within the Voronoi region need to send the environmental information to the Voronoi vertex, that is the cluster head in *WSN* terminology. This method always optimizes the communication links from a sensor node to the cluster heads and it is very useful for saving communication energy because the communication energy expenditure is directly proportional to the distance travelled by the data packets.

The *Multihop Voronoi LEACH (MV-LEACH)* was presented to enhance the *Vor-LEACH* in terms of reducing the communication energy expenditure

[23]. The primary idea of this method is to use the multi-hop nature of communication between sensor nodes and their relevant cluster heads within the Voronoi region. It computes direct link cost value of a path and the multihop cost value of the path. The value of *MC* must be always lesser than or equal to *DC* value. There could be multiple paths between *SN* and *CH* that satisfies the condition $DC \leq MC$. However, the *MV-LEACH* chooses a path, which has the lowest *MC* value among the multiple paths for the transmission of data. Nevertheless, the method may not sustain high volume of data transfers if the battery power of any sensor node in the path contains low level. In the next section, the paper proposes a new method that enhance the longevity of data transfers between *SN* and *CH*.

3. CONTRIBUTIONS

The lifetime of the *WSN* depends on the residual energy in network's sensors. Hence, energy efficient methodologies are given higher significance in the research area of *WSN*. The energy consumption during communications is much higher compared to the energy consumption during computations in *WSN* [8][9][20]. There are few works focused on reducing the communication energy consumption [10][11][23]. Contrary to the traditional works, the author proposed a structural change in clusters of *WSN* by introducing the Voronoi region [5][19]. A paper introduces the multihop transmissions between an *SN* and its *CH* within Voronoi region [23]. However, the method may not perform well for high volume of data to be transferred from a sensor node to the cluster head. To address this problem, in this section, we present a new method called Reliable Multihop Voronoi *LEACH (RMV-LEACH)*, which is a robust and the method avoids communication disruptions due to the low battery power levels in the sensors during the data transmissions between a sensor to *CH*.

The proposed method *RMV-LEACH* assumes that all the sensors are homogeneous and contain the same characteristics on the communication and sensing functions. The coverage of sensing and communication areas of an *SN* are Omni directional. Algorithm 1 shows the methodology used for *RMV-LEACH*.

Algorithm 1: *RMV-LEACH*

1. With the eq. (1), identify cluster heads as mentioned in *LEACH*.
2. For all the cluster heads, identify the 2-hop neighborhood information and broadcast it.
3. Construct the Voronoi diagram using localized algorithm given in [5][6] with the set of cluster heads identified in *Step 1*.
4. Using *Algorithm 2*, find the robust path from an *SN* to its *CH*.
5. Transfer environmental data of a sensor node to *CH* through the robust path obtained from *Step 4*.
6. At every specific period, a new set of *CHs* are computed and repeat steps from *Step 2* to *Step 5*.

Algorithm 1 uses the procedures of electing the cluster heads given in the *LEACH* protocol [4]. Once the cluster heads are opted, the equivalent Voronoi diagram needs to be constructed with the given set of cluster heads obtained from the *step 1*. The *RMV-LEACH* uses the localized algorithm for constricting the Voronoi diagram given in the paper [19]. The Voronoi diagram optimizes the distances between sensor nodes and cluster heads. Here, all the sensor nodes within the Voronoi region transfer the sensing information to the Voronoi vertex, i.e. cluster head. The *RMV-LEACH* used Algorithm 2 to identify the robust path from *SN* to its cluster head. The robust path avoids communication disruptions and assures high volumes data transfers between *SN* and *CH* within the Voronoi region. The *step 6* of *RMV-LEACH* adopts the dynamics of the cluster heads by recomputing a new set of *CHs* followed by repeating the steps from step 2 to step 5.

Algorithm 2 is used to identify a robust path of every sensor node to its *CH*. In the beginning, it initializes *Reliable_Path_Vector* for every sensor node and the *Residual_Energy_Threshold* values. The *Reliable_Path_Vector* stores all the paths from a sensor node to its *CH* with certain conditions. Every sensor node calculates the Direct-link Cost (*DC*) value. The *DC* value is termed as square value of Euclidean distance from a sensor node to its *CH*.

$$DC = \text{dist}(x, CH)^2 \quad (2)$$

Algorithm 2: Robust Path Identification

1. Initialize *Reliable_Path_Vector* and *Residual_Energy_Threshold* values.
2. For every sensor node *x* in the Voronoi region with cluster head *CH*, compute the direct link cost
3. For every sensor node *x*, which belongs to the Voronoi vertex *CH*, identify the intermediate node set K_i , where $K_i \notin \{x, CH\}$.
4. Compute the *MC* value

$$MC_x = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{inter_dist}(x, K_i, CH)^2$$

5. If the *MC* value is less than the *DC* value, then store the entire path in the *Reliable_Path_Vector*.
6. For every set of intermediate sensor nodes, repeat *step4* and *step5* and store all paths in *Reliable_Path_Vector*.
7. For every path $\overline{xV_iCH}$ in the *Reliable_Path_Vector* with the sequence of intermediate sensor nodes V_1, V_2, V_3, \dots , remove the path from *Reliable_Path_Vector* if any of the sensor nodes $RE\{V_i\} < \text{Residual_Energy_Threshold}$.
8. Identify the Average Residual value for every path in the *Reliable_Path_Vector*

$$AR = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n RE_x + RE_{ki} + RE_{CH} \right) / (n + 2)$$

9. Select the highest *AR* value path from the *Reliable_Path_Vector* and store it in *Robust_Vector* as robust path.
10. Return *Robust_Vector*

For every sensor node, identifying the Multihop Cost (*MC*) for paths from sensor node 'x' to its cluster head 'CH' within the Voronoi cluster.

$$MC_x = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{inter_dist}(x, K_i, CH)^2 \quad (3)$$

Here, the K_i represents intermediate sensor node within their communication range. For example, Figure 3 shows the K_1K_2 , K_2K_3 , K_3K_4 , and K_4K_5 as edges of intermediate nodes in the communication range of each other. The notation K_1K_2 indicates communication link between sensors K_1 and K_2 , which is the Euclidean distance between them. Hence, $MC_{x,CH}$ value calculated from equation (3) as

$$MC_{x,CH} = \text{dist}(x, K_1)^2 + \text{dist}(K_1, K_2)^2 + \text{dist}(K_2, K_3)^2 + \dots + \text{dist}(K_5, CH)^2 \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: Multihop within a Voronoi region

After calculating the MC values, the sensor nodes verify whether the MC value is less than the DC value. If it is lesser then it stores the path in the *Reliable_Path_Vector*. The process is repeated for all the possible paths from sensor 'x' to the cluster head 'CH' with the intermediate sensor nodes within a Voronoi region. After all the paths are gathered in *Reliable_Path_Vector*, it identifies the *Robust_Vector* from the *Reliable_Path_Vector*. To compute the *Robust_Vector*, it deletes all paths from the *Reliable_Path_Vector* if any sensor node in the path has lower residual energy than the threshold value *Residual_Energy_Threshold*. These paths are considered weak paths as the node's battery power may deplete sooner if bulk data transfer occurs. After deleting the weaker paths from the *Reliable_Path_Vector*, for every path, it calculates the Average Residual (AR) value. The average residual value is defined as

$$AR = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n RE_x + RE_{ki} + RE_{CH} \right) / (n + 2) \quad (5)$$

Here, RE_x , RE_{ki} , and RE_{CH} represents the residual energy of sensor 'x', intermediate mediate SNs, and the CH , respectively. AR value exists for every path in the *Reliable_Path_Vector*. Once the AR value is available, then it selects the highest AR value path as the robust path and stores it in *Robust_Vector*. The robust path is used for transfer of environmental data from SN to its CH . The robust path increases the network lifetime without any communication interruptions during the sensor data transfer from SN to CH .

4. SIMULATIONS

The simulations have been conducted with the tools network simulator (*ns2*) and the python programming. The *ns2* generates different node scenarios in a square grid of $100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$. The random distribution of sensor nodes for different numbers of nodes is considered for simulations. These set of nodes are of sizes 20, 25, 30, and 35. The communication range of a sensor node is 25 meters. In the proposed method, it is assumed that all sensor nodes have the same communication range and sensing range. The *RMV-LEACH* considered a *Residual_Energy_Threshold* value as 50% of its total battery power. Each sensor node is provided with a maximum of 100 Joules of energy at the beginning of the simulation. There are few experiments conducted to analyze the performance of *RMV-LEACH* protocol.

The first experiment is conducted to analyze the robustness of the path, which is used to transfer sensed information from a sensor SN to its cluster head CH within its Voronoi region. In the analysis of the simulation, it considers only one Voronoi region, CH , SN , and multiple relay sensor nodes, which are neighbors of the CH . The reliable path vector collects all the paths from the SN to CH . The robust path vector is computed by selecting the maximum average residual energy of sensor nodes existing in the path between SN and CH . Figure 4 shows the lowest residual energy of any sensor node between SN and CH in the robust path. From the graph, it indicates that the proposed method path contains higher values on residual energy of sensors compared to *MV-LEACH*'s path and it can guarantee a higher amount of data transfers without any communication interruptions. Similarly, Figure

5 shows average residual energy in the robust path of *RMV-LEACH* and low-cost path of *MV-LEACH*. From the graph, it shows that *RMV-LEACH* contains higher levels of residual energy compared to *MV-LEACH*, and it can be used for a higher volume of data transfers.

Figure 4: Minimum Residual Energy

The next experiment is conducted to analyze the *multihop cost* and *direct-link cost* of a path from *SN* to *CH* within a Voronoi cluster for three protocols *Vor-LEACH*, *MV-LEACH*, and *RMV-LEACH*. The *Vor-LEACH* contains only *DC* values, whereas *MV-LEACH* and *RMV-LEACH* use both *DC* and *MC* values in the protocol. From Figure 6, it shows that the path cost is highest for *Vor-LEACH* protocol. However, the path cost for protocol *RMV-LEACH* is higher than *MV-LEACH* because *MV-LEACH* does not consider residual energy levels, instead it greedily extracts lower distance values in *MC* calculations. Nevertheless, the *RMV-LEACH* takes care of the possibility of intermediate node failures in the path, which provides robustness to the communication path.

Figure 5: Average Residual Energy

Figure 7 shows the hop count of the path while transferring the information from *SN* to its *CH*. From the figure, it is observed that *Vor-LEACH* contains the hop count as always one, whereas *RMV-LEACH* and *MV-LEACH* may contain more than one hop count value because of its multihop nature. Sometimes, *RMV-LEACH* contains lower hop count values than *MV-LEACH* as it avoids some nodes in the path due to the lower residual energy levels in the battery. Figure 8 shows the number of neighbors while building the *RMV-LEACH* protocol. Note that the number of neighbors considered only for one cluster. From figure, it is observed that the number of neighbors are directly proportional to the total number of sensors within same area of node distribution. Note that the number of neighbors are important in identifying multiple paths for the *Reliable Path Vector*. In general, more neighbors lead to higher number of paths in path vector.

Another experiment is on finding the maximum data to be transferred on the paths of *MV-LEACH* and *RMV-LEACH* without communication interruptions, which occur due to the low energy levels in the sensor nodes. The energy consumption model considers transmission energy consumption (*ETx*) as 4.602 $\mu\text{J}/\text{bit}$ and receiving energy consumption (*RTx*) as 2.34 $\mu\text{J}/\text{bit}$ [26]. Note that if any node in the path reaches zero battery power, then it cannot transfer the data, and the path is considered invalid. In the experiment, it has taken one *SN*, its assigned *CH*, and all the intermediate sensor nodes in the path between *SN* and *CH*. For *RMV-LEACH*, it considers all the nodes in the robust path and transfers the data through these nodes. For *MV-LEACH*, it considers low-cost *MC* path for transferring the data. We have plotted the graph for maximum data that can be transferred through robust path for *RMV-LEACH* and low-cost *MC* path for *MV-LEACH*. Figure 9 shows that the *RMV-LEACH* can transfer higher volumes of data compared to *MV-LEACH* because the *RMV-LEACH* eliminates the sensors with low battery levels, whereas the *MV-LEACH* does not consider it.

The next experiment is on identifying the maximum number of transmissions for packets (blocks) of different sizes 512 bytes, 1024 bytes, 2048 bytes, 3072 bytes, and 4096 bytes. The experiment considers 35 sensor nodes in the simulation with *ETx* and *RTx* values as 4.602 $\mu\text{J}/\text{bit}$ and 2.34 $\mu\text{J}/\text{bit}$, respectively. From Table I, it shows that the *RMV-LEACH* can sustain a higher number of transmissions compared to *MV-LEACH*. This could happen because the robust path in *RMV-LEACH*

has higher levels of residual energy and can transit more data compared to *MV-LEACH*. Another observation from *Table 1* is that the number of transmissions is reduced by increasing the data block size.

Table 1: Number of Transmissions vs Data Blocks

Data Block Size (Bytes)	MV-LEACH	RMV-LEACH
512	48	398
1024	24	200
2048	12	100
3072	8	67
4096	7	57

Figure 6: The MC and DC values

Figure 7: Hope count of the path

Figure 8: Number of Neighbors Within the Cluster

Figure 9. Maximum Data Transfer

5. CONCLUSIONS

In *WSN*, the sensors have limited energy in their battery and a sensor is considered dead if its battery power is exhausted. Hence, the research community of *WSN* gives high priority for energy saving mechanisms in network. In the literature, several energy efficient clustering mechanisms for *WSN* are reviewed to describe how they enhance energy consumption in the network for various *LEACH* protocols. In the article, a new energy efficient clustering method *RMV-LEACH* is proposed. The proposed method identifies a robust path within the Voronoi region from an *SN* to its *CH*. This robust path can sustain higher volumes of data transfers between *SN* and *CH*, which is common in many sensor network applications. The simulation is carried out for the proposed method and the results show the performance of the *RMV-LEACH*.

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